

**WHAT MATTERS MORE FOR SUCCESSFUL MASTERING OF
COMPUTER SCIENCES, TYPE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL OR
WEEKLY ALLOCATION?**

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***Abstract.** The article describes the results of the research done at the Faculty of Operation And Economics of Transport And Communications of the University of Žilina. There were several research objectives. The first goal was to find out the impact of the type of secondary school on the results of the study at the university from the subjects of Informatics in both semesters. The second objective was to find out how the number of hours in the subject of informatics weekly attended at secondary school affects the grade from Informatics at the faculty. The third goal was to compare study results in both semesters. To obtain the results was used the One-Factor Variance Analysis Method, T-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances, t-Test Paired Two Sample for Means.*

The research points out that study results of university students are to a large extent influenced by a quality and type of a secondary school. Type of secondary school influences the results of the students not only in the 1st semester

but as well in the 2nd semester. Difference in the grades in both semesters are significantly better in favour of Grammar Schools.

Another interesting fact was that students who had a lot of informatics in secondary school do not achieve better results than those who have much less of Informatics. The research has pointed out, that more than two hours weekly allocation of computer science lessons per week, doesn't lead to better outcomes in the subject Informatics at the university.

As it turned out, the grades in the 2nd semester, the performance of the students in the second semester were significantly better than in the first semester. This confirmed the assumptions of the teachers, who noted a significant improvement in the lectures of the second semester. Students work more on exercises and lectures and communicate much more with educators and teachers.

From this it can be concluded that some students adapted to the situation, improved their academic results and were able to move on to the next grades.

Keywords: *Informatics, One-Factor Variance Analysis, Two-Sample T-Test Unequal Variances, Paired t-Test.*

Introduction. At this time, it is not possible to imagine any activity without up-to-date technologies and using IT has become an essential part of our lives. Working life requires the use of the computer by professionals in all areas. Therefore, it is necessary to include the subject of Informatics in the program for all levels of school education.

Informatics is a relatively new subject compared to mathematics. As a result, there has been much less research done in IT education.

The level of students coming to the University of Žilina is very different. There are significant differences in the level of knowledge from secondary schools,

in the way of study, in the approach to the responsibilities and, finally, in the pursuit of new knowledge. Many students have difficulties integrating fully into the study process and are having problems to master the study of the first year.

Therefore, research was conducted to find out what is the big difference between students, which is affecting their achievements.

Analysis of recent research and publication. In recent years were encountered several problems that affect not only the learning results but also the teaching process itself. Moreover, the problems have a negative impact on the professional quality of the lectured subject matter in exercises and lectures.

Teachers often meet with the inability of most students to work systematically throughout the term, which means:

- During the teacher's explanation, they do not concentrate on the subject matter explained as they are not able to focus on learning.
- Tasks in exercises are done only superficially.
- Students do not rely on their abilities and do not like it if the teacher asks them to try to perform the tasks themselves without help.

Another problem is studying for an exam. Many students are not interested in acquiring more profound knowledge. They are not interested in mastering the subject as best as possible. Most of the effort is spent on passing an exam, learning only basics and getting the grade from the exam.

One of the reasons may be narcissism, which is described, and its consequences are explained in the article by the author Podzimek, M. from 2019 in Problems of narcissism in education: The culture of narcissism as a dangerous global phenomenon for the future. It is the narcissism observed in young people that can have undesirable effects both concerning studies but also in relation to

authorities, i.e., university professors and teachers. It is a consequence of modern times.

Modernism, which appeared as a result of industrialization, has since then developed further, resulting in a postmodern society, characterized by a significant change in values. This shift in values is particularly evident in the quality of education, and man's subsequent relation towards work as a result. Schools have become social institutions in which learners spend their time in the role of served clients. The teacher is therefore assigned the social role of the servant, in which he is to satisfy the pupil in his personal needs primarily. This kind of relationship stems from the phenomenon of narcissism, which is already a cultural phenomenon (Podzimek, M. 2019, p.489).

Furthermore, it can be one of the problems why students in schools do not have such quality results as they can achieve based on their prerequisites.

Another reason why some students have difficulty in studying at a university may be the Massification of higher education. Another reason why some students struggle with the studies is the fact that university also accepts students who should not have studied at all at the university some decades ago, now they can attend universities and also the curriculum is too challenging for them. As mentioned in the article of Vančíková K. (2019), however, the massification of higher education is a natural response of society to the new demands of the era and it is logical to assume that by the end of the 21st century the vast majority of the population will have higher education. Slovakia lags behind the OECD and EU average in this indicator. The issue is not how many students head towards higher education but what programs they are heading for. Massification is a problem or challenge for university education worldwide, as evidenced by the authors' work of Deane E. Neubauer, D., E., Ka Ho Mok, Jin Jiang. (2017) in work *The Sustainability of*

Higher Education in an Era of Post-Massification. Series: Routledge Critical Studies in Asian Education. The book researches the sustainability of mass university education across the Asia-Pacific region and its consequences, challenges and particular country constraints. Over the last three decades, the massification of university education has been through in complex and in some cases overwhelming ways. Moreover, both universities and secondary schools must adapt their teaching programs to a new trend.

Probably the most significant change in the way of study has been brought by the Internet.

Interaction and Information technologies have reshaped our life today, and nowadays' students and teachers have massive use of smartphones, iPads and other portable devices; moreover, they are continually looking for cutting edge technologies (Alabdulkareem, S. 2018, p.583).

The Internet is a phenomenon we cannot imagine our life and work without. This phenomenon has its pros and cons.

Here is described some aspects of its negative influence on university studies.

- Impact of web pages on knowledge
- The vast amount of information available to everyone and everywhere. It is difficult to determine which information is relevant and can be used as reliable.
- Mobile networks and connectivity to the Internet

It allows students to surf the Internet during lessons that distract their attention from gaining knowledge.

It allows cheating on exams to an extent which was never seen in history before.

Research Focus. Mentioned problems are less evident in certain groups of student. Teachers were interested in what may affect the achievement of students at universities.

Students at first filled in questionnaire in which they specified type of secondary school attended, number of Informatics lessons per week, location of secondary school etc. Out of these information and expertise of university teachers there were main areas of research determined – how the type of secondary school and the number of lessons of informatics weekly affects the results of the subject Informatics at the university.

Research Aim and Research Questions. The article describes verifying the following research issues:

- Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence students' 1st semester study results in the subject Informatics1.
- The impact of the number of lessons per week in secondary school on the grade from the subjects of Informatics1.
- Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 2nd semester study results in the subject Informatics2.
- The impact of the number of lessons per week in secondary school on the grade from the subject of Informatics2.
- Grades of both semesters. Whether there is improvement during second term, whether students learned to work more effectively during classes, to look out and study from literature and to prepare for successful passing of the exam.

Research Methodology. One of the problems teachers observed during lectures and exercises is the knowledge level of students coming from different

secondary schools - it is related to the type of school. Students from different types of schools have:

Different quality of knowledge

Different learning habits and different abilities to learn new topics and a different approach when preparing for an exam.

The article describes verifying the following research issues:

- *Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 1st semester study results in the subject Informatics1.*

On the sample of 290 students from the faculty of operation and economics of transport and communications of the University of Žilina, the achieved marks of the subject Informatics1 are compared according to individual secondary schools. To obtain the results was used the method the One-Factor Variance Analysis Method.

Therefore the research group was divided into three groups: the first group consisted of 98 students from Grammar Schools, the second group consisted of 94 students from Business Academies and the third group consisted of 98 students from Secondary Technical Schools from all over the Slovakia and other European countries.

- *The impact of the number of lessons per week in secondary school on the grade from the subjects of Informatics1.*

For this purpose, was used T-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances. The research group was divided in two groups – the first group consisted of students with more than two lessons of computer science per week at a secondary school and the second group of students whose lesson allocation was less or equal than 2 hours per week.

- *Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 2nd semester study results in the subject Informatics2.*

In the second semester, research was conducted on a sample of 182 students participating in the exam. These are the same students as in the first semester, but the number is lower because some students have dropped out early and some have failed the exam and will repeat the subject in the second year. For this purpose was used the method the One-Factor Variance Analysis Method.

- The impact of the number of lessons per week in secondary school on the grade from the subject of Informatics2 using T-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances on sample of 182 students.

- Grades of both semesters while using the method of t-Test Paired Two Sample for Means.

Data Analysis - the 1st Semester

Verifying following research issues - Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 1st year study results in the subject Informatics1.

Secondary schools were divided into three categories according to the type of secondary schools in Slovakia:

Grammar School

Business Academy

Secondary Technical School.

Based on these observations, were identified the following research issues:

Whether and to what extent can the type of secondary school influence their 1st year study results in the subject Informatics1?

To study this, there were used the grades of 290 students and average grade from an IT exam was calculated for every type of secondary school. This shows that a type of secondary school affects students' results at university (Table 1).

Table 1. The Average Grade in the Informatics1 Exam according to the Type of School

Grammar School	3,11224
Business Academy	3,69474
Secondary Technical School	3,9596

For statistical evaluation of the results obtained in the experiment, was used one - factor variance analysis (Tirpáková, A. 2011). It was expected that the level of the mean of three primary complexes depends on one factor – type of secondary school (Table 2).

Table 2. Anova Single Factor

Anova: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
Column 1	98	305	3,112245	2,203766042		
Column 2	94	346	3,680851	1,875543354		
Column 3	98	388	3,959184	1,750894172		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	36,48622	2	18,24311	9,382641431	0,000113	3,027221
Within Groups	558,0276	287	1,944347			
Total	594,5138	289				

Teachers were also interested in the fact, which two of three are significantly different in their effectiveness. The MS Excel program does not operate with statistical programs for these kinds of file comparisons; therefore was used Duncan's test for the statistical significance of contrasts.

The average numbers of points were arranged according to their size.

$$\bar{x}_1 = 3,11; \quad \bar{x}_2 = 3,68; \quad \bar{x}_3 = 3.$$

The value of tested criterion was calculated, given S_r^2 as a residual dispersion

$$D_p = \frac{|\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j| \cdot \sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{1}{n_j}\right) \cdot S_r^2}}; \quad p = 2,3.$$

The relevant tables were used for the determination of critical values of Duncan's test $D_{0,05}$ for the significance level $\alpha = 0,05$ for given p and given residual number of degrees of freedom $290 - 3 = 287$. These data were entered into the Table 3 together with the calculated values $D_{p,\alpha}$.

By means of these characteristics, was tested the statistical significance of the particular arithmetic averages (Šusteková, D., & Kontrová, L. 2019).

Table 3. The Critical Values of Duncan's Test

p	$D_{p,critic}$	i, j	$D_{p,0,05} = \frac{ \bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j \cdot \sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{1}{n_j}\right) \cdot S_r^2}}$
2	2,772	i = 1, j = 2	4,24
2	2,772	i = 2, j = 3	2,08
3	2,91	i = 1, j = 3	6,32

Were reviewed the results between the first and second sample: $p = 2$, $D_{2,\alpha} = 4,24$; $D_{2,\alpha} > D_{2,critic}$ thus differentia is significant,

Were reviewed the results between the second and third sample: $p = 2$, $D_{2,\alpha} = 2,08$; $D_{2,\alpha} < D_{2,critic}$ thus differentia is not significant.

Were reviewed the results between the first and third sample: $p = 3$, $D_{3,\alpha} = 6,32$; $D_{3,\alpha} > D_{3,critic}$ thus differentia is significant.

Result: There is a significant difference in learning outcomes between Grammar School and Business Academy and Grammar School and Secondary Technical School.

Business Academy and Secondary Technical School do not have a significant difference.

The results show that students from Grammar Schools are best prepared for university studies.

Verifying following research issues - Whether students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two hours weekly (group1) in a secondary school achieved better results in the Informatics1 than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 lessons per week (group2).

The study results are pointing out that the number of computer science lessons per week at secondary schools does not affect the learning results. It is shown by the average grades of both student groups (Table 4):

Table 4. The Average Grade in the Exam Informatics1 according to the Number of Hours of Computer Science Lessons in a Secondary School per Week

Number of hours per week > 2	3,568627451
Number of hours per week ≤ 2	3,675675676

This fact was surprising for teachers, so they decided to verify it. Based on the formulation of the pedagogical experiment's aim the following hypothesis was set:

H_1 : The students with more than two lessons of computer science per week at a secondary school achieved better results in the Informatics1 exam than the students whose lesson allocation was less than 2 hours per week.

To verify the hypothesis H_1 , was selected a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. There were compared two groups of data: in the first set, there were results from the examination of students with higher allocation.

There were two independent files $n = 36$, $m = 255$. There were calculated sample characteristics by using an F – test. It was found out that the difference between their distributions is not statistically significant. For this reason was tested the difference between the two groups by a two-sample location Student's t-test with equal distribution.

There was tested the hypothesis $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ versus $H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$

The value of test statistics is $T = 0,26018$ and $p = 0,7949$.

When comparing it with the critical values of a t-test were obtained:

$T = 0,2601 < t_{0,05}(289) = 1,9682$.

The H_0 hypothesis was not rejected. The selective average on the selected significance level does not differ from the value of the average of the basic file (Šusteková, D., & Kontrová, L. 2019).

The results of the statistical analyses did not confirm our expectations. There were obtained the following results: Students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two lessons (group1) a week at a secondary school do not achieve better results in the Informatics1 exam than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 hours a week (group2).

Table 5. Results of T-Test Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

<i>t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances</i>		
	Variable 1	Variable 2
Mean	3,638888889	3,57254902
Variance	2,408730159	2,001605682
Observations	36	255
Pooled Variance	2,050911414	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	289	
t Stat	0,260181256	
P(T<=t) One-Tail	0,397454616	
t Critical One-Tail	1,650143229	
P(T<=t) Two-Tail	0,794909233	
t Critical Two-Tail	1,968206436	

Data Analysis - the 2nd Semester

In the second semester, research was conducted on a sample of 182 students participating in the exam. These are the same students as in the first semester, but the number is lower because some students have dropped out early and some have failed the exam and will repeat the subject in the second year.

Verifying following research issues - Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 1st year study results in the subject Informatics2

The calculation of grade averages by type of secondary school (Table 6) indicated that the type of secondary school still has an impact on student performance. Table 6 shows that the order of success of students according to secondary schools is the same as in the first semester, i.e., the best is Grammar School, then Business Academy and then Secondary Technical School.

Table 6. The Average Grade in the Informatics2 Exam according to the Type of School.

Grammar School	2,38
Business Academy	2,778
Secondary Technical School	2,932

For statistical evaluation of the results from the experiment, was used one - factor variance (Tirpáková, A. 2011). It was expected that the level of the mean of three basic complexes depends on one factor – the type of secondary school (Table 7).

Table 7. Anova Single Factor

Anova: Single Factor						
SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
5	85	203	2,388235	1,454622		
4	17	48	2,773529	1,404412		
5	88	258	2,931818	1,604493		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	13,16606	2	6,583028	4,330791	0,014502	3,04424
Within Groups	284,2497	187	1,520052			
Total	297,4158	189				

Because the $F > 3,0272$ is valid, the H_0 hypothesis was reject at the significance level $\alpha = 0,05$, which means that the level of students' knowledge from different schools A, B and C are significantly different.

The same result is obtained by the use of value *Value P*. As the value $P = 0,014502$, the value of error was get if the null hypothesis is rejected and it

is approximately 1,45 %, which is allowable error rate at the significance level $\alpha = 0,05$.

Duncan's test was used for the statistical significance of contrasts again.

The average numbers of points were arranged according to their size.

$$\bar{x}_1 = 2,38; \quad \bar{x}_2 = 2,77; \quad \bar{x}_3 = 2,93.$$

The value of tested criterion was calculated, given S_r^2 as a residual dispersion

$$D_p = \frac{|\bar{x}_i - \bar{x}_j| \cdot \sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n_i} + \frac{1}{n_j}\right) \cdot S_r^2}}; \quad p = 2,3.$$

The relevant tables were used for the determination of critical values of Duncan's test $D_{0,05}$ for the significance level $\alpha = 0,05$ for given p and given residual number of degrees of freedom $192-3 = 189$. These data were entered into the Table 8 together with the calculated values $D_{p,\alpha}$.

By means of these characteristics, there was tested the statistical significance of the particular arithmetic averages.

Table 8. The Critical Values of Duncan's Test

p	$D_{p,critic}$	i, j	$D_{p,0,05}$
2	2,80	$i = 1, j = 2$	1,83
2	2,80	$i = 2, j = 3$	0,73
3	2,95	$i = 1, j = 3$	4,27

Were reviewed the results between the first and second sample: $p = 2$, $D_{2,\alpha} = 1,83$; $D_{2,\alpha} < D_{2,critic}$ thus differentia is not significant.

Were reviewed the results between the second and third sample: $p = 2$, $D_{2,\alpha} = 0,73$; $D_{2,\alpha} < D_{2,critic}$ thus differentia is not significant.

Were reviewed the results between the first and third sample: $p = 3$, $D_{3,\alpha} = 4,27$; $D_{3,\alpha} > D_{3,critic}$ thus differentia is significant.

Result: There is a significant difference in learning outcomes between Grammar School and Secondary Technical School.

However, there is no significant difference between Grammar School and Business Academy and between Business Academy and Secondary Technical School.

The results of the second semester also confirm that Grammar School students are best prepared for the studies at the university.

Verifying following research issues - Whether students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two hours weekly (group1) in a secondary school achieved better results in the Informatics2 than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 lessons per week (group2).

The study results are pointing out that the number of computer science lessons per week at secondary schools does not affect the learning results of Informatic2. It is shown by the average grades of both student groups (Table 9):

Table 9. The Average Grade in the Exam Informatics2 according to the Number of Hours of Computer Science Lessons in a Secondary School per Week

Number of hours per week > 2	2,67
Number of hours per week ≤ 2	2,55

It was verified by T-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances.

Evaluating the hypothesis statistically by T-Test for Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances.

There were two independent files $n = 75$, $m = 118$. For this reason there was tested the difference between the two groups by a two-sample location Student's t-test with unequal variances.

There was tested the hypothesis $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ versus $H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$

Results were in Excel file (Table10).

Table 10. Results of T-Test Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances		
	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean	2,76	2,52991453
Variance	1,536216216	1,47539051
Observations	75	118
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	156	
t Stat	1,264796754	
P(T<=t) One-Tail	0,103915192	
t Critical One-Tail	1,654679996	
P(T<=t) Two-Tail	0,207830384	
t Critical Two-Tail	1,975287508	

The value of test statistics is $t = 1,2647$ and $P = 0,1039$. When comparing it with the critical values of a t-test were obtained: $t = 1,264 < t_{0,05}(183) = 1,975$.

The H_0 hypothesis was not rejected. The selective average on the selected significance level does not differ from the value of the average of the basic file.

Comparison of Results after Passing the Subjects of Informatics1 and Informatics2

This section evaluates the results of the exams Informatics1 and Informatics2 of the 1st year of study. The aim was to find out how the student's results changed in the 2nd semester,

The method used for this evaluation was t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means (Table 11)

Table 11. t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	1.semester	2.semester
Mean	2,653846154	3,417582418
Variance	1,641946451	2,178252687
Observations	182	182
Pearson Correlation	0,240451907	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	181	
t Stat	-6,03919081	
P(T<=t) one-tail	4,29592E-09	
t Critical one-tail	1,653315758	

There was set up and tested the hypothesis

H0 – the results in the 1st semester and 2nd semester are identical

compared to the hypothesis of

HA – the results in the 2nd semester are on average better compared to those in the 1st semester.

There was used t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means.

The P-value of the test is approximately 4.3E-9; therefore, the hypothesis H0 was rejected and thus, HA is valid.

Thus, it has been shown that the student results in the second semester were significantly better than in the first semester. This confirmed the assumptions of

the teachers who observed a significant improvement in the second semester lectures. Students work harder in exercises and lectures and communicate much more with educators and teachers.

Research Results

The first research issue was:

Whether and to what extent can the type of secondary influence their 1st year study results in the subject Informatics1?

Following results were achieved:

- There is a significant difference in learning outcomes between Grammar School and Business Academy, and Grammar School and Secondary Technical School,
- Business Academy and Secondary Technical School do not have a significant difference in learning outcomes.

The results show that students from Grammar Schools are best prepared for university studies.

The second research issue was:

Whether students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two hours weekly in a secondary school achieved better results in the Informatics1 than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 lessons per week.

The results of the statistical analyses did not confirm our expectations. There were obtained the following results: Students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two lessons a week at a secondary school do not achieve better results in the Informatics1 exam than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 hours a week.

The third research issue was:

Whether and to what extent can type of secondary school influence their 1st year study results in the subject Informatics2

Following results were achieved:

- There is a significant difference in learning outcomes between Grammar School and Secondary Technical School.

- However, there is no significant difference between Grammar School and Business Academy and between Business Academy and Secondary Technical School.

The results of the second semester also confirm that Grammar School students are best prepared for the studies at the university.

The fourth research issue was:

Whether students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two hours weekly at a secondary school achieved better results in the Informatics2 than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 lessons per week.

It was confirmed the same as in the 1st semester – Students with a higher number of lessons in computer science than two lessons a week at a secondary school do not achieve better results in the Informatics2 exam than students whose lesson allocation was equal or less than 2 hours a week.

The fifth research was set up and tested the hypothesis

H0 – the results in the 1st semester and 2nd semester are identical

compared to the hypothesis of

HA – the results in the 2nd semester are on average better compared to those in the 1st semester.

Grades in the 2nd semester shows that students consecutively get used to university load, they find the way to learn and work sufficiently so they are able to fulfill studying demands.

Discussion. The research points out that study results of university students are to a large extent influenced by a quality and type of a secondary school. Difference in the grades in both semesters are significantly better in favour of Grammar Schools.

Historically, Grammar schools in Slovakia prepare students for studies at university. It is natural that their graduates have best results. Grammar Schools offers general education, so their graduates are prepared to continue on any type of university. Other two types of secondary schools mentioned in the article are more technical and practical and only partially oriented on preparation for university.

Despite all this it is necessary to think about overall knowledge level of students coming to university.

According to university teacher's experiences students in general don't have sufficient knowledge as well as studying habits. For example, chancellor of Slovak Technical University decided to launch "zero year" which should prepare secondary school graduates for study at their university. It would be desired if secondary schools increase demands on teachers what will result in better quality of these schools. The teachers are most important. It is needed to have superior and devoted teachers and the education will improve. (Mokošová Z. 2020).

Very interesting is finding about computer science allocation per week. It is surprising that number of computer science hours per week doesn't influence the grade from this subject at the university. One of the reason is that student's knowledges are motly limited to only practical use – e-mail, social networks;

surfing on the internet and playing games. Deeper knowledge is missing, this needs to be learned at the university. Grades in the 2nd semester shows that students consecutively get used to university load, they find the way to learn and work sufficiently so they are able to fulfill studying demands.

Conclusions and Implications. Even though the Informatics is taught at every level of education in Slovakia (starting in elementary school) the results of the research are surprising. Type of secondary school influences the results of the students not only in the 1st semester but as well in the 2nd semester. The best results are accomplished by students from Grammar Schools which are in Slovakia considered as schools with the highest standard and quality of education. This might have been partially expected.

Very surprising is the fact, that more than two hours weekly allocation of computer science lessons per week, doesn't lead to better outcomes in the subject Informatics at the university. Also worth of taking a note is the research outcome related to significant improvement in student's studying results in the second semester. This might be considered by secondary school teachers when creating weekly schedule. Recommendations based on the research related to better knowledge base of secondary school graduates in IT area would be on one hand not to increase weekly allocation, allocation of two hours per week seems to be sufficient but to focus on deeper knowledge of computer science and the way how students should prepare and work on the classes.

As demonstrated grades in the 2nd semester student results in the second semester were significantly better than in the first semester. This confirmed the assumptions of the teachers who observed a significant improvement in the second

semester lectures. Students work harder in exercises and lectures and communicate much more with educators and teachers.

Acknowledgments. This article was written as a part of the research project MŠ SR KEGA 055ŽU-4/2021 Modernization of system of mathematical education of the students of the technical sciences with the use of the multimedia applications Pa.

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